

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Box 3.8 The spread of invasive alien species on Japanese tsunami marine debris

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Project leader and contributors:

- Morelia Camacho-Cervantes (m.camachocervantes@gmail.com)

Data curator(s):

- Morelia Camacho-Cervantes (m.camachocervantes@gmail.com)

- Ryoko Kawakami (r-kawakami@iges.or.jp)

Description

Section 3.3.3.4 assesses the role of solid waste as a driver of biological invasions in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: Tsunami AND driven AND rafting

Search 2: [Articles using Carlton 2017 as a reference]

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

- **Searched time period:**

Search 1&2: 1900 to 2019

- **Date:**

Search 1&2: 5 August 2021

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

Search 1: 1 (1 paper selected for review)

Search 2: 144 (6 papers selected for review)

Selection criteria:

Articles that discussed the Japan Tsunami as a vector of introduction for IAS

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 0

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):

Number of papers reviewed: From the initial 145 papers found, the first scan included reviewing from the title and abstracts which ones were the most representative for the section, the ones that could include information on the Tsunami marine debris as a vector of introduction for IAS were fully read, and then 7 were selected to draft the section.

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)